

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION OF GLASS/EPOXY INTERFACES

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SUMMARY

The construction of force fields for Coarse Grained Molecular Dynamics simulations directly from *ab initio* calculations is presented in this paper. The force fields are then applied in the modeling of a glass-epoxy interface comprising an extensively cross-linked epoxy system and a silane to study its mechanical response to tensile loads.

Keywords: Composite interfaces, Crosslinking, Coarse-grained, Molecular Dynamics, Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation is a popular approach to obtain detailed molecular motions in interfaces and has attracted growing interest with the rapid development of computer technology and fast algorithms [1]. In molecular dynamics simulations of polymers, the motions and interactions of the atoms inside the function groups of the chains can often be ignored if the polymer system is large enough. One or more function groups can be treated as one “big atom”, or bead. Therefore, only the motions and interactions between such beads need to be considered [1-4].

In the present study, a glass/epoxy interfacial system crosslinked with a coupling agent, gamma amino-propyl-triethoxysilane (AMPTES), was modeled and simulated with coarse grained bead-spring molecular dynamics. *Ab initio* molecular dynamics was used to develop an interbead bond force field that not only controls the motion of the beads but also allows for bond breakage within the polymer chain network. The mechanical properties of the interfacial system obtained from the coarse grained model through the simulation of tensile loading to failure are presented and the relationship between the yield stress and bond strength is elucidated.

DESCRIPTION OF COMPOSITE INTERFACE

For the glass fiber reinforced epoxy system being investigated here, the interfacial region comprises a glass fiber and epoxy matrix with the coupling agent gamma amino-propyl-triethoxysilane (AMPTES). In addition to the crosslinking reactions, the C-O bonds of the epoxy group are broken and crosslinked with the amino function groups on the AMPTES to form polymer chain networks at the glass-epoxy composite interface.

COARSE GRAINED MOLECULAR MODEL OF GLASS-EPOXY INTERFACE

The molecular structure of glass-epoxy interface with AMPTES is shown in Fig. 1. Two AMPTES silane molecules are bonded onto the glass surface while the amino-groups on the other end of the silane molecules are bonded with the two epoxy groups at the ends of an epoxy molecule chain. The different circles represent the beads in the mapping strategy of the coarse grained model. The molecular system with the bead mapping strategy comprises a total of eight different pairwise bonds connecting nine beads.

Fig. 1 Molecular structure of crosslinked glass-epoxy interface with AMPTES.

DESCRIPTION OF COARSE-GRAINED FORCE FIELD

A coarse grained force field for the system is formulated and parameterized using *ab initio* MD calculations. The present force field comprises a potential to account for the valence interaction between beads that are bonded together and a Lennard Jones non-bond potential to describe the van der Waals force interactions between beads.

In constructing the force field for the valence interaction between beads, only bond stretching energy was considered. It is expected that for a highly crosslinked polymer chain network under tension such as the epoxy interface system considered here, bond stretching accounts for most of the potential energy.

The valence potential employed in this study comprises a Lennard-Jones type potential and a Morse potential. A broken bond is not allowed to form again in the simulation. The Morse potential accounts for small changes in bond lengths about the equilibrium while the Lennard-Jones potential provides large repulsive forces when beads move close to one another. Another Lennard-Jones potential is used to represent the van der Waals forces among all the beads.

PARAMETERIZATION OF COARSE-GRAINED FORCE FIELD

The force field for each pair of bonded beads is determined directly from quantum mechanics calculations. Material Studio [5], with its CASTEP and DMol3 modules, was used to obtain the geometrically optimized structures and to obtain the relationships between the bonding energies and bonding distances of neighboring bead pairs shown in Fig. 1. Each pair of the beads was modeled with atomistic detail. All valence atoms bonded to the structural unit are replaced with protons [6]. Geometry optimization calculations were then performed using CASTEP for the bead pairs to obtain the equilibrium conformation. Based on the optimized configurations, the bonding energies as a function of interbead distance were determined for each pair of beads. The force field was then parameterized using least squares fitting methods of the DMol3 results.

To obtain the valence interaction between the two beads, a series of configurations were built by displacing one of the two beads by different amounts. *Ab initio* MD calculations were then performed to obtain the corresponding valence energy of each strained configuration. The force required to displace a bead is obtained from the gradient of the potential function.

When the beads are pulled apart, the valence forces increase to a maximum before tapering off to zero. A cut-off distance is assigned for each bead pair. This cut-off distance determines the maximum bond length before the valence bond breaks and cannot reform again. We define bond breakage to occur when the bead pairs have stretched by three times the elongation corresponding to the maximum interatomic force. The least square fitting algorithm was used to fit the interbead potentials obtained from the *ab initio* calculations.

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Based on the mapping strategy in Fig. 1, a system of epoxy adhesive film between two glass walls is constructed in a manner similar to that described by Stevens [7, 8]. The epoxy adhesive is contained between two rigid walls with period boundary conditions applied on boundaries perpendicular the walls. A tensile load is applied along the direction perpendicular to the walls to study the tensile response of the system. In the present model, each wall consists of two layers of beads. The outermost layer represents the surface of the glass fiber and each bead consists of three Si atoms. The inner layer consists of beads h . The bonds between the two layers correspond to bond $h-i$ in Fig. 1. These are very strong Si-O bonds which are not expected to break during the tensile loading. Thus, the bead pair $h-i$ is treated as rigid. In the present simulation, all Si atoms are bonded to AMPTES molecules to represent full wetting of the fiber. The present coarse grained molecular dynamics simulation is performed at constant temperature T using the Rouse Model [3, 4].

In the construction of the initial configuration of the interfacial system, segments of the polymer chains in Fig. 1 are first regularly arranged without crosslinking and then subjected to heating to initiate crosslinking and achieve equilibrium. The regular structure before crosslinking and equilibration is shown in Fig. 2. Beginning from each wall is a layer i beads. The AMPTES molecules are then fully pre-bonded to the wall beads, i.e., from each i bead is connected a chain comprising beads h to a as indicated in Fig. 1. The head and tail beads, a and e , are the crosslinkers and are capable of bonding with two other crosslinker beads. There are a total of 28200 beads in this system with dimensions $L_x=30R_0$, $L_y=19.5R_0$ and $L_z=21.5R_0$. R_0 , the length scale in the LJ potential is also the lattice dimension of the regular structure. The initial crosslinked configuration is obtained under a Langevin thermostat with $T=1.1e$ while keeping the two walls rigid but free to move.

Fig. 2 Initial regular structure of interfacial system before crosslinking, Grey and red beads correspond to the beads i and h in Fig. 3. Blue and pink beads between the walls are used to distinguish the different layers of beads.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the initial crosslinked structure is obtained, the mechanical properties are studied by pulling the upper wall along the z direction at a velocity of $0.02R_0/\tau$ away from the fixed bottom wall. The loading process is performed under constant temperatures of $T=0.3e$, $0.7e$ and $1.1e$. The stretching simulation was also performed at different velocities of $v=0.06R_0/\tau$ and $0.002R_0/\tau$ under constant temperature at $T=0.3e$ to compare the results of different strain rates below glass transition temperature.

Figure 3 shows snapshots of the crosslink system at strains of a) 0.2 , b) 0.4 and c) 0.8 under isothermal loading at a temperature of $T=0.3e$. The cohesive failure from void initiation to propagation is clearly shown. The stress-strain curve is plotted in Fig. 4 together with those at temperatures of $T=0.7e$ and $1.1e$. It shows that there are three stages of deformation for all the three temperatures. At a strain of about 0.08 , there is a first peak in stress, which corresponds to the yield stress. This yield is mainly due to the van der Waals forces between the beads reaching a maximum. Any extension beyond this will therefore be accompanied by a drop in the load. The second stage is a plateau stage. The stress remains relatively constant at this stage because the stress is transferred from the van der Waals bonds to the valence bonds of unfolding chain segments. The third stage begins when the folded bead chains have aligned to the direction of loading and begin to stretch beyond their equilibrium length. At this stage the stress is sustained by the bond stretching until at some point, valence bonds begin to break. More voids are generated and they propagate until the system finally ruptures and the interfacial system is completely severed.

Fig. 3 Coarse grained model of crosslink system at tensile strains of a) 0.2 , b) 0.4 and c) 0.8 at $T=0.3e$

Fig. 4 Tensile stress-strain curve for the crosslinked system under constant temperature at $T=0.3e$, $0.7e$ and $1.1e$.

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References

1. Baschnagel J., Binder K., Doruker P., Gusev A. A., Hahn O., Kremer K., Mattice W.L., Muller-Plathe F., Murat M., Paul W., Santos S., Suter U.W. and Tries V., *Adv. Polym. Sci.*, 2000, 152, 41-156.
2. Muller-Plathe F., *CHEMPHYSICHEM*, 2002, 3, 754-769.
3. Kremer K., and Grest G., *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1990, 92/8, 5057-5086.
4. Kremer K., and Grest G., *Entanglement Effects in Polymer Melts and Networks*, in *Monte Carlo and Molecular Dynamics Simulations in Polymer Science.*, (Binder K., ed.), Oxford: New York, 1995, 194-271.
5. Accelrys Inc., *Material Studio*, Copyright 2001-2007, Accelrys Inc.
6. Hopfinger AJ and Pearlstein RA, *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, 1984, 5/5, 486-500.
7. Stevens M.J., *Macromolecules*, 2001, 34, 1411-1415.
8. Stevens M.J., *Macromolecules*, 2001, 34, 2710-2718.